

CV Template Synthesis

Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI)-like Narrative CV: Template Synthesis

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Purpose

This R4RI-like narrative CV template synthesis aims to provide a summary of the ways in which R4RI-like narrative CV templates are being used by some of the members of the [Joint Funders Group](#) members. R4RI is based on

the Royal Society's [Résumé for Researchers \(R4R\)](#) but has been adapted to be more inclusive of UKRI's research and innovation communities.

Table 1: Summary of findings

Across a sample of 10 funders in January 2022 the following was observed:

CV template contains a section aligned to Résumé for Researchers (R4R) section head								
Funder	Personal details	Module 1: How have you contributed to the generation of knowledge?	Module 2: How have you contributed to the development of individuals?	Module 3: How have you contributed to the wider research community?	Module 4: How have you contributed to broader society?	Personal statement	Additions	ORCID iD
1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
2	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
4	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
7	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Synthesis of findings

Extent of use

- Most (6/10) of the R4RI-like narrative CVs have been or are currently being used (including use within pilots) in at least one of the funder's opportunities; 4/10 plan to pilot use from 2022.
- All funders require Principal Investigator (lead applicant) to complete an R4RI-like narrative CV, most (6/10) also require completion by Co-Principal Investigator (co-applicant/co-leads); not all funding opportunities using the R4RI-like narrative CV allow for Co-Principal Investigators (co-applicants/co-leads). One funder additionally requires R4RI-like narrative CV completion by collaborators and mentors, and one funder intends to require completion by all named staff.

Template headers/sections

- All funders ask applicants for personal details; however most (6/10) do not include this specific ask within the CV template as these details are collected elsewhere within the application process.
- All funders use the question headings/sections for modules 1, 2 and 3 from the Royal Society R4R template using the same or similar wording.
- 8/10 funders employ the module 4 question with the same or similar wording. One of these funders combines modules 1 and 4 in a single header. Another funder combines module 3 and 4 in single header. One funder identified perceived challenges with the limited assessment guidance for reviewers for Module 4 being a deterrent factor in its current use.

All funders include 'Additions'. Four of these CV templates have the section titled 'Career Breaks' rather than 'Additions'. One indicated within supplementary guidance that this information could be included within the Personal Details section. One funder includes the 'Additions' section in a separate part of the application form from the R4RI-like narrative CV.

Although not a header/section within the R4RI-like narrative CV template, the majority (7/10) provide space within the application for applicants to include their ORCID iD (a persistent digital identifier), with 2 funders providing an explicit location for the ORCID iD within the CV template.

Word/Page length of CVs

- The length of the CV and sections varied across the R4RI-like narrative CV templates with some (4/10)

highlighting word count limits per section and a few (3/10) indicating a page length limit. The lengths/limits of the remaining (3/10) are not determined as they are yet to be piloted.

- Of those (4/10) providing word limits:
 - one provided a total word limit across the four modules of 1,000 words, with no word limit on the personal statement
 - two provided word limits that varied by module; however, both allocated a higher word limit to Module 1 (500 or 300 words) compared to the other modules (which varied from 300 to 200 words)
 - one planned a consistent word limit of 250 words per section
 - no funders indicated minimum word requirements
- Of those (3/10) providing page limits:
 - this varied from between a maximum of two to five pages
 - one funder provided a varying page limit depending on the role of the individual completing the R4RI-like narrative CV (Lead Applicant and Co-Applicant or Collaborator and Mentor).
 - no funders indicated minimum page requirements.
- Some funders noted consideration of reviewer capacity and grant system set-ups/limitations being a determining factor in the decision of setting word vs page limits.

Common features

- An illustrative example showing the common features of the CV template can be found in the Annotated R4RI-like narrative CV template in the [Résumé Resources Library](#).

Next Steps

- There is an aspiration to revisit the CV template synthesis with updated information in light of reviews and evaluations.

Version Number	Status	Revision Date	Author(s)	Summary of Changes
1.0	Complete	March 2022	Joint Funders Group	New resource created
2.0	Complete	May 2023	Joint Funders Group	Proof-edited and designed